

Could lithium reverse the progress of Alzheimer’s disease? Review of “Lithium deficiency and the onset of Alzheimer’s disease”

Ondrej Eliáš

Abstract

A research team at Harvard Medical School has made findings that could have a radical impact on our understanding of AD’s development and potentially present a new hope for people suffering from this devastating disease. The study was published in August 2025 in the journal [Nature](#). It was shown that lithium, a humble metal already used as a treatment of bipolar disorder, plays a crucial role in preventing cognitive decline, memory loss, learning impairment, neurodegeneration and that its deficiency significantly contributes to the development of AD’s hallmarks. These new findings support the results of a [study from Denmark](#) that reported an important inverse correlation between prevalence of dementia and Li levels in drinking water.

Introduction

To understand the complexity of this topic, two concepts need to be explained at first: the accumulation of phospho-tau (tau tangles) and the deposition of amyloid-beta (amyloid plaques) which are the two hallmarks of Alzheimer’s disease.

1. Accumulation of phospho-tau

Tau is a protein that normally stabilizes microtubules, which mediate transport of nutrients in neurons. When too many phosphate groups attach to the tau-protein, it becomes hyperphosphorylated and can’t bind to microtubules. Tau-proteins clump together forming neurofibrillary tangles. This hampers the transport of nutrients in neurons and consequently damages them, leading to neuronal and synaptic dysfunction and cognitive decline.

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

2. Deposition of amyloid-beta

Amyloid- β peptides ($A\beta$) are protein fragments derived from APP (Amyloid Precursor Protein), which can form clusters in the brain. Their harmfulness depends on their length. The longer they are, the greater their tendency to build clumps and the more deleterious they are for the brain. The brain can use several mechanisms to remove these amyloid proteins. However, in Alzheimer's disease these mechanisms fail to function properly, leading to the buildup of amyloid plaques. These plaques are located between the neurons, disrupting neuronal communication and causing damage.

Figure 3:

Study Summary

Altered Metal Levels

In the study, brain tissue samples from three distinct cohorts were analysed. Each cohort contributed tissue from the prefrontal cortex (PFC), a region significantly affected in Alzheimer's disease, as well as from the cerebellum, which typically remains unaffected. The first cohort consisted of individuals exhibiting no clinical signs of Alzheimer's disease (NCI). The second cohort comprised individuals diagnosed with mild cognitive impairment (MCI), while the third cohort included individuals with advanced Alzheimer's disease (AD).

Figure 4:

The tissue/serum ratio (how much of the metal is present in brain tissue compared to blood serum) of 27 different metals was measured. Several metals in patients with Alzheimer's disease showed changes in their abundance in PFC (prefrontal cortex) compared to patients with no signs of AD. Li showed the most striking discrepancy, with its significantly reduced levels in the PFC. Thus, lithium levels were lower in brains with MCI than in those with NCI and were even lower in patients with AD.

Figure 5:

Impact of Li on the two hallmarks of Alzheimer's disease (amyloid plaques and phospho-tau accumulation)

It was shown that lithium accumulates in the amyloid plaques in the brains of patients with MCI or AD. In PFC of people with AD or MCI, lithium was significantly reduced due to its accumulation in the plaques. The greater the severity of the disease, the more Li gets trapped in the plaques. Low Li-levels also correlated with reduced episodic and semantic memory, as well as with a reduced index of global cognitive function. The results suggest that this trapped Li is less available for the neurons and consequently that this leads to a malnutrition of the cells.

Li-deficient diet:

In other part of the study, mice were maintained on a lithium-reduced diet (92% reduction). Only five weeks after the start of this diet, a greater amyloid plaque load was observed, which continued to increase with adherence to the Li-reduced diet. A β 42 (the most toxic and pathogenic amyloid associated with AD) levels were increased in the hippocampus as well as in the cortex. The results also indicate that removal of lithium from the diet galvanizes phospho-tau accumulation in neurons. Eventually, it was shown that "Li-deficient diet significantly impaired learning and long-term memory."

After this period of Li-deficient diet, transcriptome of the mice was analysed, with results proving that transcriptome and proteome are markedly influenced by endogenous Li. The number of different cell types remained unchanged, nonetheless significant changes of transcriptome of various cell types were observed. Pathways promoting neurodegeneration and AD were upregulated, whereas pathways involved in signalling, organization and transmission were suppressed. Amount of protein associated with neuroinflammation was increased.

Lithium was shown to play a crucial role in maintaining synaptic structure, integrity and signalling capacity. In Li-deficient mice, genes responsible for these functions were downregulated, abundance of synaptic proteins was reduced, myelin-related genes were suppressed, myelin sheaths were thinner and significant loss of myelin occurred. Myelin forms a protective sheath around neuronal axons, enabling rapid transmission of electrical impulses. Its damage slows down signal conduction and impairs neuronal communication.

One of the key mechanisms underlying these effects is GSK3 β . It is a kinase, meaning an enzyme that attaches a phosphate group to other molecules. It is a pivotal regulator of β -catenin signalling (protein important for gene activity), as well as for the tau, the phosphorylation of which entails tau-tangles, a hallmark of AD. Li regulates GSK3 β 's activity. With Li-deficiency, the kinase-amount and activity increases, which entails reduction of β -catenin's levels leading to disruption of cell signalling. The kinase also over-phosphorylates the tau, which gives rise to already mention tau-tangles.

Apparently, Li has also an impact on glial cells, most abundant cells in our central nervous system, different from neurons, which do not take part in synaptic signalling, have significant

importance in maintaining homeostasis, forming myelin, regulating the uptake of neurotransmitters and general maintenance of the brain and serve as immune-like cells. There are several types of glia cells, as for instance microglia, Schwann cells, oligodendrocytes etc.

Figure 6:

Microglia are important cells in our brains and one of their functions is the clearance of amyloid plaques. As the brain ages, the capacity of microglia to degrade A β declines. At the same time, with aging they also become overactive, leading to increased inflammation in the brain.

According to the study, in lithium-deficient microglia, genes linked to DNA repair, stress responses and protein breakdown become downregulated, resulting in a decreased ability to protect the brain. Conversely, genes linked to Alzheimer's pathways, amyloid plaque formation and oxidative stress become upregulated, resulting in impaired removal of amyloid and increased inflammation. Overall, these lithium-deficient microglia cells display a stark resemblance in their transcriptome to AD microglia.

New Hope for the future?

Li occurs naturally in salts. One of the most common lithium salts used in medicine is lithium carbonate (LiC). The problem with lithium is that it dissolves in the brain and easily gets trapped in the A β plaques, preventing it from being properly utilized by the brain cells.

Within the framework of the study, the conductivity of different lithium salts was measured with the objective to find out which salts dissolve more easily and which harder, resulting in either higher or lower tendency to bind the aggregated forms of A β , leading to plaques, a hallmark of AD. As previously, experiments were conducted on mice genetically modified to bear the traits of AD. After the administration of LiC, lithium was still strongly present in amyloid plaques, whereas after the administration of lithium orotate (LiO), lithium occurred

in much smaller amounts in these plaques. It was shown that LiO much more effectively leads to elevated levels of non-plaque lithium than LiC does. In 3xTg mice which were provided with water containing LiO, A β sequestration was significantly diminished, as well as the phospho-tau accumulation! It was shown to reverse the loss of microglia's ability to degrade A β ! On the contrary to that, the effects of LiC and sodium orotate were far from having that significant effect. LiO was also more effective in reducing microgliosis (activation and increase in number of microglial cells leading to increased inflammation) and astrogliosis. Genes associated with pathways of neurodegeneration, β -catenin degradation and AD were downregulated, whereas the genes connected to learning or memory, synapse organization or signalling were upregulated. LiO almost completely reversed the memory loss, improved spatial memory and learning, suppressed neuroinflammation and synapse loss.

Conclusions

This study represents a significant breakthrough in Alzheimer's research. It not only demonstrates that lithium is essential for maintaining neuronal and glial function, but also shows that its deficiency significantly contributes to the formation of amyloid plaques, tau tangles, and neuroinflammation, and thus to the development of AD.

Importantly, the findings reveal that lithium orotate provides a form of lithium that remains bioavailable in the brain and can reverse many of these pathological changes in animal models, including memory and learning deficits. These results open an exciting avenue for developing new lithium-based treatments that could fundamentally alter the progression of Alzheimer's disease and offer new hope for patients worldwide.

Literature:

1. Aron L, Ngian ZK, Qiu C, Choi J, Liang M, Drake DM, Hamplova SE, Lacey EK, Roche P, Yuan M, Hazaveh SS, Lee EA, Bennett DA, Yankner BA. Lithium deficiency and the onset of Alzheimer's disease. *Nature*. 2025;633(7858):234–242. Available from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-025-09335-x>
2. Cell Signaling Technology. Neurodegeneration: Tau protein and neurofibrillary tangles. *Cell Signaling Blog* [Internet]. [cited 2025 Aug 23]. Available from: <https://blog.cellsignal.com/neurodegeneration-tau-protein-and-neurofibrillary-tangles>
3. Drummond E, Pires G, MacMurray C, Askenazi M, Nayak S, Bourdon M, Safar J, Ueberheide B, Wisniewski T. Phosphorylated tau interactome in the human Alzheimer's disease brain. *Brain*. 2020;143(9):2803–2817. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32812023/>
4. BrightFocus Foundation. What are Alzheimer's plaques and tangles? [Internet]. [cited 2025 Aug 23]. Available from: <https://www.brightfocus.org/resource/what-are-alzheimers-plaques-and-tangles/>
5. National Center for Biotechnology Information. *Amyloid precursor protein*. In: NCBI Bookshelf [Internet]. 2014 [cited 2025 Aug 23]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK4282969/>
6. National Institutes of Health. *Myelin*. In: MedlinePlus [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2025 Aug 23]. Available from: <https://medlineplus.gov/ency/article/002261.htm>
7. National Center for Biotechnology Information. *Glial cells*. In: NCBI Bookshelf [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2025 Aug 23]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK10869/>
8. National Center for Biotechnology Information. *Neuroinflammation*. In: NCBI Bookshelf [Internet]. [cited 2025 Aug 23]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK441945/>

Figures:

Figure 1: *Neuronal cytoskeleton*. Adapted from Roychowdhury S, Sierra-Fonseca JA. In: *Heterotrimeric G Proteins and the Regulation of Microtubule Assembly*. IntechOpen; 2017. Available from: <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/53624>

Figure 2: *Comparison of functional and hyperphosphorylated tau*. Adapted from Giong HK, Subramanian M, Yu K, Lee J-S. Non-Rodent Genetic Animal Models for Studying Tauopathy: Review of Drosophila, Zebrafish, and C. elegans Models. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2021;22(16):8465. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22168465>

Figure 3: *Major pathological hallmarks of AD*. Adapted from De Loof A, Schoofs L. Alzheimer's Disease: Is a Dysfunctional Mevalonate Biosynthetic Pathway the Master-Inducer of Deleterious Changes in Cell Physiology? *OBM Neurobiol*. 2019;3(4):46. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337715716_Alzheimer%27s_Disease_Is_a_Dysfunctional_Mevalonate_Biosynthetic_Pathway_the_Master-Inducer_of_Deleterious_Changes_in_Cell_Physiology

Figure 4: Figure X: *Prefrontal cortex and cerebellum: visualisation*. Adapted from Palesi F, Tournier J-D, Calamante F, et al. Contralateral cerebello-thalamo-cortical pathways with prominent involvement of associative areas in humans in vivo. *Brain Struct Funct*. 2015;220(6):3369–3384. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/264867225_Contralateral_cerebello-thalamo-cortical_pathways_with_prominent_involvement_of_associative_areas_in_humans_in_vivo

Figure 5: *Lithium deficiency and the onset of AD*. Adapted from Aron L, Ngian ZK, Qiu C, et al. Lithium deficiency and the onset of Alzheimer's disease. *Nature*. 2025;633(7858):234–242. Available from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-025-09335-x>

Figure 6: *Types of neuroglia cells*. Adapted from Blausen.com staff. *Medical gallery of Blausen Medical 2014*. WikiJournal of Medicine. 2014;1(2). Available from: https://en.wikiversity.org/wiki/WikiJournal_of_Medicine/Medical_gallery_of_Blausen_Medical_2014